

A Comparative Study on Job Satisfaction of School Teaching and College Teaching Staff at Tuticorin Town

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Introduction

When I take a long time-I am slow; when my boss takes a long time-He is thorough. When I don't do it- I am Lazy, when my boss doesn't do it- He is too busy. When I do something without being told- I am trying to be smart, when my boss does the same- That is initiative. When I please my boss- That's apple-polishing, when my boss please his boss-He's co-operating. When I am good- My boss never remembers, when I do wrong- He never forgets. India has become important in the worldwide education market, with a large number of its students seeking higher education in different countries such as U.S., Europe., U.K. and Australia. It also is opening up its domestic market to foreign universities, which therefore would have a great in being a part of this growth. It is also a large market for cases and other education materials.

The first millennium and the few centuries preceding it saw the flourishing of higher education at Nalanda, Takshashila., university, ujjain and vikramshila universities. Among the subjects taught were Art, Architecture, painting. Logic, mathematics, Grammar, philosophy, Astronomy, Literature, Buddhism, Hindusim, Arthashastra (Economics and politics) law and medicine. Each university specialized in a particular field of study. Takshila specialised in the study of medicine, while Ujjain laid emphasis on astronomy. Nalanda being the biggest centre, handled all branches of knowledge, and houss up to 10,00 student at its peak.

Growth of Eduaction in India

Education in India provided by the public sector as well as the private sector with control and funding coming from three levels, federal, state, and local. Child Education is compulsory. The Nalanda University was the oldest university-system of Education in the world.

Western Education became ingrained into Indian society with the establishment of the British raj. Education in India falls under the control of both the union government and the states, with some responsibilities lying with the union and the states having autonomy for other. The various articles of the Indian constitution provide for Education as a fundamental right. Most universities in India are controlled by the union on the state government. India has made progress in terms of increasing primary Education attendance rate and expanding literacy to approximately two thirds of the population. India's improved education system is often cited as one of the main contributors to the economic rise of India. Most of the progress especially in Higher education, scientific research has been credited to various public institutions. The private education market in India is merely 5% although in terms of value is estimated to be worth \$40 billion in 2008 and will increase to \$68 billion by 2012. However, India continues to face stem challenges. Despite growing investment in education 25% of its population is still illiterate only 15% of Indian students reach high school, and just 7% graduate. As of 2008, India's post-secondary high school offer only enough seats for 7% of India's college-age population, 25% of teaching positions nationwide are vacant and 57% of college professors lack either a masters or PhD degree. As of 2011 there is 1522 degree-granting engineering colleges in India with an annual student's intake of 582,000, plus 1244 polytechnics with an annual intake of 265000. However, these institutions face shortage of faculty and concerns have been raised over the quality of education.

Scope of the Study

The present study is made to analyses comparatives study on job satisfaction of school teaching staff and college teaching staff in Tuticorin Town. This study includes in extended to knowing the school teaching staff and college teaching staff attitudes regarding overall job satisfaction. This study is further extended to know the expectations and find out the way of satisfying the school teaching staff and college teaching staff. The area of the study was restricting a limited number of respondents.

Objectives of the Study

- To Identify the factors that influence school teaching staff and college teaching staff in Tuticorin Town.
- To evaluate the relationship among the co-workers.
- To evaluate the student behaviors in schools and colleges.
- To identify the income from other sources school teaching staff and college teaching staff in Tuticorin Town.
- To evaluate level of satisfaction at job security of the respondents of different teaching experience.

Statement of the Problem

Job satisfaction is good not only for the employees but employers too. It increases productivity and decreases Staff Turn Over. There are two aspects are important in School and College teaching staff at Tuticorin town. Teachers are an inseparable part of the development of a country. Nearly half of the population of a country is teachers. Education is a Media through which student development can be achieved where the Youth teachers have significance role to play. The financial benefits, the rewards or punishment system, in group relationship, the culture of the institution and society etc. contribute to affecting their satisfaction.

Analysis and Interpretation**Level of Satisfaction at Job Security of the Respondents of Different Teaching Experience Observed Frequency Table**

S.No.	Teaching Experience	Job security				Total
		HS	S	DS	HDS	
1	Less than 3 years	12 (15%)	8 (10%)	1 (1.25%)	0 (0%)	21
2	3-5 years	11 (13.75%)	8 (10%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	19
3	5-10 years	7 (8.75%)	9 (11.25%)	3 (3.75%)	3 (3.75%)	22
4	Above 10 years	8 (10%)	5 (6.25%)	5 (6.25%)	0 (0%)	18
Total		38	30	9	3	80

Hypothesis

There is no relationship between teaching experience of the respondents and level of satisfaction in their job security.

Null Hypothesis

There is relationship between teaching experience of the respondents and level of satisfaction in their job security.

The table elucidates that among 38 respondents who have highly satisfied in their job, it includes, 19 respondents who have (23.75%) feel their class room environment are highly satisfied, 14 respondents who have (17.5%) feel their class room environment are satisfied, 3 respondents who have (3.75%) feel need to improve, 2 respondents who have (2.75%) feel their class room environment are highly dissatisfied. Among 30 respondents who have satisfied in their job, it includes, 12 respondents who have (15%) feel their class room environment are satisfied, 18 respondents who have (22.5%) feel need to improve. Among 9 respondents who have dissatisfied in their job, it includes, 2 respondents who have (2.5%) feel their class room environment are highly satisfied, 3 respondents who have (3.75%) feel their class room environment are satisfied, 3 respondents who have (3.75%) feel need to improve and 1 respondents who have (1.25%) feel their class room environment are highly dissatisfied. Among 3 respondents who have highly dissatisfied in their job, it includes, 1 respondents who have (1.25%) feel their class room environment are highly satisfied, 2 respondents who have (2.75%) feel their class room environment are highly dissatisfied. Chi-square test has been applied. Table 3.36 depicts the working of chi-square test.

Chi-Square Test for the Level of Satisfaction at Job Security of the Respondents of Classroom Environment

S.No.	Cell	O	E	O-E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² /E
1	R1C1	19	10.45	8.55	73.1025	6.9954
2	R1C2	0	8.25	-8.25	68.0625	8.25
3	R1C3	2	2.48	-0.48	0.2304	0.0929
4	R1C4	1	0.83	0.17	0.0289	0.0348
5	R2C1	14	13.78	0.22	0.0484	0.0003

6	R2C2	12	10.89	1.11	1.2321	0.1131
7	R2C3	3	3.26	-0.26	0.0676	0.0207
8	R2C4	0	1.09	-1.09	1.1881	1.09
9	R3C1	3	11.4	-8.4	70.56	6.1894
10	R3C2	18	9.0	9.00	81.00	9.00
11	R3C3	3	2.7	0.3	0.09	0.03333
12	R3C4	0	0.9	-0.9	0.81	0.9
13	R4C1	2	2.38	-0.38	0.1444	0.0606
14	R4C2	0	1.88	-1.88	3.24	1.88
15	R4C3	1	0.56	0.44	0.1936	0.3457
16	R4C4	2	0.19	1.81	3.2761	17.2426
Total						52.2488

Degrees of Freedom = (C-1) (R-1) = 4-1x4-1
 = 3x3 = 9

Calculated value of χ^2 = 52.2488

Table value of χ^2 0.05 = 16.92

The calculated value of 52.2488 is higher than the table value of 5% levels of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant relationship between classroom environment of the respondents and level of satisfaction in job security of the respondents.

Level of Satisfaction at Job Security of the Respondents of Different Teaching Experience Observed Frequency Table

S.No.	Teaching Experience	Job security				Total
		HS	S	DS	HDS	
1	Less than 3 years	12 (15%)	8 (10%)	1 (1.25%)	0 (0%)	21
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4	Above 10 years	8 (10%)	5 (6.25%)	5 (6.25%)	0 (0%)	18
Total		38	30	9	3	80

Source: Primary data

Hypothesis

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The table elucidates that among 38 respondents who have highly satisfied in their job, it includes, 19 respondents who have (23.75%) feel their class room environment are highly satisfied, 14 respondents who have (17.5%) feel their class room environment are satisfied, 3 respondents who have (3.75%) feel need to improve , 2 respondents who have (2.75%) feel their class room environment are highly dissatisfied. Among 30 respondents who have satisfied in their job, it includes, 12 respondents who have (15%) feel their class room environment are satisfied, 18 respondents who have (22.5%) feel need to improve. Among 9 respondents who have dissatisfied in their job, it includes, 2 respondents who have (2.5%) feel their class room environment are highly satisfied, 3 respondents who have (3.75%) feel their class room environment are satisfied, 3 respondents who have (3.75%) feel need to improve and 1 respondents who have (1.25%) feel their class room environment are highly dissatisfied. Among 3 respondents who have highly dissatisfied in their job, it includes, 1 respondents who have (1.25%) feel their class room environment are highly satisfied, 2 respondents who have (2.75%) feel their class room environment are highly dissatisfied. Chi-square test has been applied. Table 3.36 depicts the working of chi-square test.

Conclusion

There is research on Job Satisfaction among the School and College teaching staff and they analyzed the term Job Satisfaction from Job security. But this study can be termed as a Government College and School teaching staff, private college and school teaching staff of Job satisfaction. Here the term Job satisfaction is analyzed from school and college institution.

Job satisfaction is the fulfillment of one's expectation from their job. It is a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's Job experience. It may differ from person to person, place to place, job to job, context to context, management to management. So Job satisfaction cannot be generalized. The Job satisfaction is affect the following factors, Administration of management, policy, culture of that institution, working environment, supervisory style affects the Job satisfaction. This satisfaction will then be inferred to the students and next to the nation.

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